

ISSUES IN WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND ITS IMPACT ON EMPLOYEES: A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract

Rapid economic growth associated with cut throat competition in job market has been affecting work life balance. Striking a balance between professional and personal life is at most importance to achieve personal and professional goals. The aim of this paper is mainly on work-life balance, its significance and issues affecting physical, mental state, occupational, emotional, social, spiritual and environmental wellbeing of employees. Drawing a balance between work life and professional life, acts as a strong driving force for employees to go forward. Thus, it results win- win situation for both employees and employers in terms of personal satisfaction and higher productivity respectively.

Keywords: Work-Life Balance, Job Satisfaction, Stress, Impact.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid economic growth associated with cut throat competition in job market has been affecting work life balance. Striking a balance between professional and personal life is at most importance to achieve personal and professional goals. The aim of this paper is mainly on work-life balance, its significance and issues affecting physical, mental state, occupational, emotional, social, spiritual and environmental wellbeing of employees. Drawing a balance between work life and professional life, acts as a strong driving force for employees to go forward. Thus, it results win- win situation for both employees and employers in terms of personal satisfaction and higher productivity respectively.

Objectives

- To understand the conception of Work- Life Balance.
- To review the need, significance and therefore scope of Work-Life Balance.
- To review the issues from different sectors for Work-Life Balance and establish gaps from the present analysis.

METHODOLOGY

This study review literature from articles, journals. Its attempt to discover ideas and zones where studies were explored identified with balance between work and life and future scope for research.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This paper is a detailed review of earlier exploration of work (1986-2020) in the field of Work-Life Balance. Likewise, different ideas which made significant commitment around there, their real relevance and furthermore the future exploration scope has been distinguished.

Beverly H Burris (1986) conducted study to understand the impact of work stress on working mothers and their family. It found that there are a lot of limitations no flexible working hours, lot of part time job which leads to failure of maintaining the work life balance of working women.

Lisa young, Brian H Kleiner (1992) examines work and family conflicts faced by the employees during 1990s. It was revealed that the focus on work life includes factors like childcare, family responsibilities, family holidays, flexible working hours and affects the work life balance of women employees.

Barbara white, Daryl O Connor, Lisa Garrett (1997) this study conducted to identify the stressors faced by women doctors during their career establishment and early 30's and after that. It was found that certain measures were taken in order to maintain the careers of women doctors in hospital such as creating work friendly environment, company improved climates etc. In order to maintain work life balance.

Jan Selmer, Alicia S M Leung (2002) this paper speaks about Career management issues of female business expatriates and understands the difficulties faced by women entrepreneurs in managing their career. It found that women entrepreneurs often fail or have less chances to achieve their career goals when compared to men, it was mainly due work life balance. This paper talks about issues

Susanna lo (2003) conducted a study among 50 female professional with children in Hong Kong to understand about the difficulties faced by married women in maintaining their work life balance. It observed that the women led a stressful life and the work life balance is not achieved. It is found that the not providing flexible working hours being the main reason behind the women having a stressful lifestyle.

Doirean Wilson (2003) studied about the problems faced by female politician in maintaining work life balance. It found that the women face conflicts in work life balance and the major factors being childcare, digital technology, gender, work-life strategies.

Nathalie Lapeyre (2003) conducted study to explore the view of Professional and domestic work arrangements of women general practitioners in France and found that women have more problems in managing family and work life when compared to men. It was mainly due to the society roles, support and family responsibilities and hence they adopt various strategies to manage work life and family life.

Mary L Gatta, Patricia A Roos (2004) study conducted to know about the relation between family life and that of work life. The study reveal that the family life and work life conflicts are seen affecting the career and that the women lack support to strike a conventional balance of job space and family space...

Helen Lingard, Kerry Brown, Lisa Bradley, Caroline Bailey, Keith Townsend (2007) conducted a study in construction Industry in Wivenhole Alliance. To study about HR policies and strategies which yield some advantage of the workers as well as the company. It found that majority of the employees in the Wivenhole Alliance were highly satisfied and happy with their work life balance. It also revealed that the connection between the work life balance, professional job timings and that of the productivity played an important role.

Claire Dambrin, Caroline Lambert (2008) study conducted in Big Four in France to study the relation between motherhood and that of a working women and the difficulties faced by them and found that meeting the expectations from the society and that of the organisation itself is big conflict. And due to thus reason it is difficult to find women employees in the top level management of an organisation.

Souha R Ezzedeem, Kristen G Ritchey (2009) examine about the conflicts faced by females in maintaining their work life balance of executive women, it found that factors like family support, work support, values and ordering or ranking of personal and professional works play an important role in work life management.

Stefanos K Giannikis, Dimitrios M Mihail (2010) empirical analysis conducted to understand about the women's career part time problems and adverse situations faced by women and their motivating factors in retail sector, Greek. It found that both full time and part time women employees were same in understanding the job motivations, part time women employees were found to be optimistic and work environment also had an impact on motivating the employees.

Vanishree (2012) study conducted in Hyderabad to understand the need of work life balance strategies from the BPO employees point of view and to understand its effect on their family life. It found that the employees were unhappy with the home demands policy and also employees were most satisfied with the work environment in context of meeting their targets.

A Meenakshi, Dr Metilda Bhuvaneshwari (2013) conducted study among BPO employees to understand work strategies of BPO and the advantages they get from organisation. The study revealed that a major part of the employees felt a requirement of increase in the salary and other basic needs. Salary and compensation plays an important role in increasing the quality of life.

Suganya.V, Dr. V. Sasirekha (2014) research was done to understand the work life balance, difficulties of female workers in BPO sector and their consequences on their professional work. It found that size of the family had no effect on the work life balance of the employees. It also revealed that the work life balance of married and unmarried female employees was not same.

Heidi Wechtler (2018) conducted study of female self-initiated expatriates motivation to work abroad to understand about the motivators helping women to work abroad. The study found four main factors motivating women work abroad, accepting reality, major motivation, and self-identity and exposure purpose. This article talks about motivating

factors leading women to work abroad but does not mention about the plans to maintain better family life.

Manjula Devi and M. Saranya (2018) A study conducted among 249 BPO employees in Coimbatore city to understand the work life balance employees working in BPO sector and the quality of life they live, the problems faced by them. It found that relation that exists between the social factors and quality of life led by the employees of BPO sector. The gender and marital status are negatively related. It also shows how other factors like designation, age, educational qualification is having their own roles in increasing the quality of life of the employees.

Ummu Markwei, Michael Kubi, Benedict Quao, Esther Julia Attiogbe (2019) have done their study on Work-Family Balance of Female Parliamentarians in Ghana, it was found that focus led on women parliamentarians in Ghana face who suffer a major time balancing their career with personal life. The study reveals how the MPs adopt various practices like role prioritizing, social support to match the pressure and minimizing their professional work at home.

Jennifer Tomlinson, Susan Durbin (2020) study conducted with 16 female part time managers and four of their line managers in public and private sector to understand the difficulties and problems faced by the female employees who work as a part time manager. It found that a majority of female employees who worked as a part time manager faced a lot of stress and worked beyond their job timing and could not manage their work life balance. There is a need for research to be continued in order to understand the strategies which could overcome stress and other problems faced by women.

FINDINGS AND GAPS OF LITERATURE REVIEW

The large number was extracted in the form of primary data and was analyzed with both qualitative and quantitative techniques in different sectors like Information Technology, BPO, Stock exchange, construction industry, banking, police department, education sector, transportation, service sectors, politicians etc. The results of various surveys conducted on work- life balance depicts there is relatively direct relationship between professional and personal life.

Any pressure or commitment related towards work or peer pressure/ corporate politics not only affects the professional space but also have negative impact on personal life, such as taking out all the stressed rage on family members and even suffer serious mental disturbance. On the other hand, any serious complications related to family matters such as marital relationship stress and not giving enough family time leads to disturbance in the normal routine of employee due to disturbed state of mind of an employee leads to poor job performance.

So in the current and upcoming years, those organizations which provide the flexibility of work-life balance, will in a way provides quality of work –life and will be able to retain the talented employees and therefore enhances work performance and increased productivity. However, there is an inevitable need to understand the adequate work conditions or environment to maintain a quality of work-life. As it is very subjective in

nature, the organizations need to put ample of emphasis on how to tackle such problems in different situation at different level.

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